

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF SELECTED FARM PONDS OF BENEFICIARY FARMERS IN AKOLA TALUKA

S. P. Thakare^{1*}, A. R. Mhaske², R. S. Patode³, Mittal S. Supe⁴, S. C. Nagpure⁵

1* M. Tech. student, 2 Head of Department and Associate Professor, 4 Assistant Professor

Department of Soil and Water Conservation Engineering,

3 Senior Scientist (SWCE) AICRP for Dryland Agriculture,

and 5 Associate Professor (CAS) Wani Rambhapur

Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (444104), Maharashtra, India.

suyogthakare007@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study was conducted on the farm ponds in Akola taluka in year 2023-24. The data on different aspects of farm ponds and its impact was collected by conducting personal interview with farmers. Rainfall data was also collected for last 10 years and runoff was estimated with SCS curve number method. It was found that 219.92 mm runoff was generated from 791.27 mm mean annual rainfall, which was 27.23%. The generated runoff was sufficient to fill the farm ponds. With preparation of farm pond, there was 70.87% increase in irrigation. Similarly, it was also observed that the harvested water was also provided to support the protective irrigation during dry spell in kharif season. Which increased the crop yield of cotton and pigeon pea by 42.06% and 36.27% respectively. Gross monetary returns and net monetary returns of different crops under protective or supplemental irrigation was found to be in the range of Rs 60,337/ha to Rs 1,79,802/ha and Rs 30,332/ha to Rs 1,04,802/ha respectively. With B:C ratio in the range of 1.74 to 2.40 respectively.

Keywords: Farm pond, protective irrigation, impact assessment, crop production, crop economics.

Introduction

In India, rainfed agriculture constitutes nearly 60 % of net sown area and play important role in food grains production mainly coarse cereals, rice, pulses, oilseeds and cotton (Rama Rao *et al.*, 2019). However, rainfed areas are characterized by low resource base, uncertain and low rainfall with prolonged dry spells and poor soil conditions with shorter growing period (Dupdal *et al.*, 2023). Even after good monsoon, water shortage for agriculture occurs due to lack of proper rainwater management, in-situ water storage, low water holding capacity of soils, low infiltration, larger intra/inter rainfall fluctuations and high evaporation demand (Suraj Bhan, 2009). The successful production of rainfed crops largely depends on efficient soil moisture conservation, surplus runoff harvesting and its utilization for supplemental or protective irrigation (Pendke *et al.*, 2014).

Farm pond is one of the most important rain water harvesting structures constructed at the lowest portion of the farm area. Farm Pond is a dug out structure with definite shape and size having proper inlet and outlet structures for collecting the surface runoff flowing from the farm area (Reddy *et al.*, 2012). Several researchers have shown that on-farm runoff collection into dugout farm ponds and supplemental irrigation can increase and stabilize the crop production (Krishna *et al.*, 1987). On the other hand, low and uncertain rainfall and inefficient crop management leads to unstable and very poor crop yields (Adhikari *et al.*, 2009).

There are divergent views on the actual potential and scope of farm ponds for water harvesting and its likely impact on enhancing food production because of the uncertainty on availability of surface water for harvesting due to varied geographical features, soil types, slopes, rainfall and high capital investment (Sastry & Singh, 1993).

So it is important to evaluate actual potential of farm pond to analyse the farm level adoption of farm pond, their impact on productivity and any problems arises during farm pond use. It is to check the financial feasibility and ability to endure over the long term. Considering this, the present study was taken up to assess the impact of selected farm ponds of beneficiary farmers in Akola taluka.

2. METHODOLOGY

Akola district is situated in the middle east of Maharashtra state. This district is situated between north 20.17 to 21.16 latitude and east 76.7 to 77.4 longitude. The overall climate can be classified as semi-arid tropical. Normal annual rainfall is 825.34 mm, where average annual rainfall is 719.27 mm. In the district area wise largest tehsil is Akola tehsil in 7 talukas. The major part of the district comes under Purna-Tapi basin. Purna is the main river flowing through the district. Katepurna, Uma, Morna, Man and Nirguna, which are the tributaries of the Purna. The total area of Akola district is 5428 sq. km. While Akola tehsil consist area of 1134.13 sq. km.

Soil type in Akola taluka is medium with swallow soil depth, light colour and sandy loam soil. For some village specifically comes under saline soil track where soil condition is saline sodic soils with the low infiltration rate of soil, that's why it is recommended to construct dugout type farm ponds for water harvesting.

The reconnaissance surveys were conducted in Akola taluka for identification of number of farm ponds for its impact evaluation. Random sampling technique was employed to select farmers for data collection. Accordingly, 10 farm ponds were selected during year 2023-2024. For easy handling of data all 10 farm ponds are assigned with identification number (Id no.) from I1 to I10 respectively.

Also, The rainfall data for the last 10 years was collected from Maharain website (www.maharain.gov.in) and the 10-year average rainfall data was used to estimate the surface runoff potential using SCS curve number technique. Runoff was calculated using following formulas (Ponce and Hawkins, 1996),

$$Q = \frac{(P-0.3S)^2}{(P+0.7S)} \quad \dots \text{For AMC I}$$

$$Q = \frac{(P-0.1S)^2}{(P+0.9S)} \quad \dots \text{For AMC II}$$

Where,

Q = Depth of runoff, mm

P = Precipitation, mm

S = Potential maximum retention, mm

Actual dimension of the selected farm ponds was measured, recorded and compared with design dimensions obtained from the project proposal of farm pond. Based on the actual dimensions of the farm ponds design the actual storage capacity of selected farm pond was determined using Prismoidal formula. (Suresh R., 1997). It is given as:

$$V = \frac{A + 4B + C}{6} \times D$$

Where,

V = Volume of excavation, m³

A = Area of excavation at top surface m²

B = Area of excavation at mid surface, m²

C = Area of excavation at bottom surface, m²

D = Average depth of farm pond, m

After calculation of runoff and estimation of actual storage capacity water harvesting potential of farm ponds was calculated by comparing actual storage capacity with runoff generated from catchment area (Mhaske *et al.*, 2012 and Patode *et al.*, 2020). It represents ability of generated runoff is capable to completely fill the farm ponds.

Also data pertaining to crops, cropping pattern, crop yields along with farm income were collected before and after preparation of farm pond through personal interview. This data is then analyzed to assess the

impact of farm ponds on crop productivity and economic impact of farm ponds.

Results And Discussion

Runoff estimation

Based on SCS curve number technique and considering the various factors that affects the runoff, the daily runoff was estimated since 2014 to 2023. The annual runoff corresponding to annual rainfall for last 10 years is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Rainfall, runoff and percent runoff during the period from 2014 to 2023

Sr. no.	Year	Rainfall, mm	Runoff, mm	Runoff, % of rainfall
1	2014	566.2	171.8	30.34
2	2015	778.6	183.42	23.56
3	2016	862.6	209.53	24.29
4	2017	540	124.48	23.05
5	2018	687.3	181.1	26.35
6	2019	691.1	144.3	20.88
7	2020	799.1	202.32	25.32
8	2021	1148.3	333.79	29.07
9	2022	1162	427.57	36.80
10	2023	677.5	220.92	32.61
Average		791.27	219.92	27.23

Data presented in table 1 indicated that the annual rainfall in the last decade varies from 540.00 mm to 1162.00 mm. With the annual runoff also varied from 124.48 mm to 427.57 mm. The mean annual rainfall for last decade is found to be 791.27 mm which generated 219.92 mm of average runoff. Due to sandy loam soil soils (medium black soil) in this region, nearly 27.23% annual runoff was estimated, indicating a good scope of runoff harvesting in this area and thus a greater number of farm ponds may be constructed in future.

Water harvesting potential of farm ponds

Water harvesting potential of the selected farm pond was determined from estimated runoff from the corresponding area and storage capacity of the farm ponds. Rainwater harvesting potential of selected

farm ponds are presented in table 2. From table 2, it is observed that all farm ponds were able to completely filled up to actual storage capacity and flooded due to high rainfall than average rainfall in the year 2023.

Table 2. Estimated of Rainwater harvesting potential of selected farm ponds during monsoon 2023.

Id no.	Actual storage capacity, m ³	Catchment area, ha	Runoff, mm	Volume of water harvested, m ³
I1	1339.56	7.89	219.92	17354.94
I2	980.88	2.80	219.92	6157.84
I3	2581.37	4.60	219.92	10116.46
I4	1830.90	6.47	219.92	14239.95
I5	2237.51	2.83	219.92	6229.98
I6	1105.32	1.29	219.92	2837.01
I7	1236.63	6.47	219.92	14239.95
I8	2376.49	4.86	219.92	10679.96
I9	1449.36	1.50	219.92	3298.85
I10	904.80	0.96	219.92	2111.26

Impact of farm pond on irrigation potential

The information regarding protective irrigation from harvested water in farm pond, after its construction were collected and compared with the area under protective irrigation before farm pond construction. Area under protective irrigation of the farm pond beneficiary farmers is tabulated in table 3. Data presented in table 3, on area under protective irrigation indicated that, overall area under protective

irrigation before construction of farm pond was 0 ha, because there was no alternate source of irrigation in that particular region. However, after construction of farm pond total area of all 10 farmers under protective irrigation was observed to be 32.38 ha. The Increase in irrigation was found to be 70.87% after construction of farm ponds and farm pond technology was found to be effective in enhancing farmer's irrigation potential and ultimately sustaining the crop productivity.

Table 3. Area under protective irrigation in hectares under farm pond of beneficiary farmers in Akola taluka

Id no.	Type of farm pond	Total area, ha	Rainfed land, ha	Irrigated land before farm pond construction, ha	Irrigated land after farm pond construction, ha	Total irrigated land, ha	Increase in irrigation, %
I1	Unlined	7.89	7.89	0	4.05	4.05	51.32
I2	Unlined	2.80	2.80	0	1.50	1.50	53.57
I3	Unlined	4.60	4.60	0	2.50	2.50	54.35
I4	Unlined	6.48	6.48	0	6.48	6.48	100.00
I5	Unlined	2.83	2.83	0	2.83	2.83	100.00
I6	Unlined	7.29	7.29	0	4.46	4.46	61.18
I7	Unlined	6.48	6.48	0	3.24	3.24	50.00
I8	Unlined	4.86	4.86	0	4.86	4.86	100.00
I9	Unlined	1.50	1.50	0	1.50	1.50	100.00

I10	Unlined	0.96	0.96	0	0.96	0.96	100.00
	Total	45.69	45.69	0.00	32.38	32.38	70.87

Impact of farm ponds on crop production

Data on crop production was collected during interview with farmers, from them. Information of crop production by rainfed land before farm pond preparation was collected. Also data of crop production due to protective or supplementary irrigation from harvested water in farm pond during season 2023 was collected. The impact of protective or supplementary irrigations was assessed by comparing crop yields from

Table 4. Impact of farm ponds on crop production

Id no.	Crop name	Rainfed land, ha	Yield, quintal	Crop productivity before ponds, q/ha	Pond irrigated land, ha	Yield, quintal	Crop productivity after ponds, q/ha
I1	Cotton	7.89	138.00	17.49	4.05	110.00	27.16
I2	Cotton	2.80	50.00	17.86	1.50	40.00	26.67
I3	Cotton	4.60	71.00	15.43	2.50	65.00	26.00
I4	Cotton	6.48	139.00	21.45	4.05	100.00	24.69
	Sorghum	-	-	-	2.43	48.00	19.75
I5	Cotton	2.83	42.00	14.83	2.83	56.00	19.77
	Sorghum	-	-	-	2.83	53.00	18.71
I6	Cotton	7.29	108.00	14.81	3.64	88.00	24.18
	Sorghum	-	-	-	0.82	17.00	20.73
I7	Cotton	3.24	56.00	17.28	-	-	-
	Pigeon pea	3.24	28.00	8.64	3.24	38.00	11.73
I8	Cotton	2.43	36.00	14.81	2.43	48.00	19.75
	Pigeon pea	2.43	22.00	9.05	2.43	30.10	12.39
	Chickpea	-	-	-	2.43	30.00	12.35
I9	Cotton	1.50	22.00	14.67	1.50	30.00	20.00
	Chickpea	-	-	-	0.41	6.00	14.81
I10	Cotton	0.96	15.00	15.63	0.96	21.00	21.88
	Chickpea	-	-	-	0.41	5.00	12.35

Impact of reutilization of farm pond water on economics of crop cultivation

Impact of rainwater harvesting with farm pond and its reutilization for protective irrigation for dry land crops and supplemental irrigation for irrigated crops was analyzed by crop yield, gross monetary returns, net monetary returns and B: C ratio and compared with crop economics under rain fed conditions. During season, 2023 protective irrigation was provided to cotton, and pigeon pea crops particularly in dry spell in the Kharif season. Similarly, supplemental irrigation was also provided from harvested water in the farm pond to chickpea in Rabi season. Information on overall crop economics of cultivation under protective irrigation for dry land crops in Akola taluka, is presented in

Table 5. Overall crop economics of cultivated crops under protective irrigation for dry land and supplemental irrigation in Akola taluka

Id no.	Crop name	Irrigated land (ha)	Yield (Quintal)	Cost of cultivation Rs.	Gross monetary returns Rs.	Net monetary returns Rs.	BC ratio
I1	Cotton	4.05	110.00	303750	728200	424450	2.40
I2	Cotton	1.50	40.00	112500	264800	152300	2.35
I3	Cotton	2.50	65.00	187500	430300	242800	2.29
I4	Cotton	4.05	100.00	303750	662000	358250	2.18
	Sorghum	2.43	48.00	72900	154800	81900	2.12
I5	Cotton	2.83	56.00	212460	370720	158260	1.74
	Sorghum	2.83	53.00	85000	170925	85925	2.01
I6	Cotton	3.64	88	273000	582560	309560	2.13
	Sorghum	0.82	17	24600	54825	30225	2.23
I7	Pigeon pea	3.24	38.00	129600	266000	136400	2.05
I8	Cotton	2.43	48.00	182250	317760	135510	1.74

rainfed land and irrigation land. Data on these aspects are presented in table 4.

From the table it is clear that crop production of cotton and pigeon pea has increased for all the farmers due protective irrigation. Also provision of supplementary irrigations in Rabi season has made possibility to grow crop as chickpea and sorghum for some farmers, which helps the farmers to increases their annual crop production.

table 5. Data presented in table 5 on different crop economics indicated that crop yield and monetary returns increased due to irrigation as a protective or supplemental. Gross monetary returns of different crops under protective or supplemental irrigation was found to be in the range of Rs 60,337/ha to Rs 1,79,802/ha. Net monetary returns of different crops under protective or supplemental irrigation was found to be in the range of Rs 30,332/ha to Rs 1,04,802/ha.

B:C ratio of different crops under protective or supplemental irrigation was found to be in the range of 1.74 to 2.40. These BC ratios implies that there are positive returns on the provision of protective or supplementary irrigation from farm ponds, which makes the farm pond economically feasible for farmers.

	Pigeon pea	2.43	30.10	97200	210700	113500	2.17
	Chickpea	2.43	30.00	85050	163200	78150	1.92
I9	Cotton	1.50	30.00	112500	198600	86100	1.77
	Chickpea	0.41	6.00	14175	32640	18465	2.30
I10	Cotton	0.96	21.00	72000	139020	67020	1.93
	Chickpea	0.41	5.00	14175	27200	13025	1.92

Conclusion

From the result it is concluded that the study area generates good amount of runoff over seasonal rainfall, indicating good scope of runoff harvesting in the farm pond. Generated runoff was able to completely filled up the actual storage capacity of the farm ponds. Showcasing the positive water harvesting potential of farm ponds.

After construction, farm pond impact on irrigation potential by increasing the overall irrigation percentage of study area over a great extent. Thus farm pond technology was found to be effective in enhancing farmer's irrigation potential to provide protective irrigation during dry spells. Also provision of supplementary irrigation made farmers to grow Rabi seasonal crops.

From the results, it is concluded that, construction of farm ponds improves the crop productivity and also the income generated from crops of the selected farmers in the Akola taluka. Also provision of protective or supplementary irrigation from farm ponds, shows positive gross monetary returns on cost of cultivation. Which makes the farm pond economically feasible for farmers to use. Finally, we can conclude that, all these finding was made possible due to the impact assessment of selected farm ponds of beneficiary farmers in Akola taluka.

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